
The Effect of Pharmacy Service Quality on Outpatient Satisfaction at Tora Belo Regional General Hospital

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ABSTRACT: Healthcare service quality reflects the gap between patient expectations and perceptions. This study examined the influence of SERVQUAL dimensions on patient satisfaction at the Outpatient Pharmacy Installation of Tora Belo General Hospital, Sigi Regency. A cross-sectional survey of 380 outpatients was conducted using a modified SERVQUAL questionnaire and analyzed with logistic regression. Tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, and empathy significantly affected patient satisfaction, while assurance did not. Improving physical facilities, service promptness, reliability, and empathetic communication is crucial to enhance patient satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Hospital, Patient satisfaction, Pharmacy installation, Service quality

INTRODUCTION

Service quality can be defined as the degree of difference between consumer perceptions or expectations and the services actually received by consumers (Mursyid et al., 2024). In Indonesia, with the implementation of the National Health Insurance (JKN) program managed by BPJS Health, more people are accessing health services through designated facilities, including regional public hospitals (Shadrina et al., 2023).

Patient satisfaction is an indicator of service quality and has implications for service providers. Low patient satisfaction may reduce patients' intention to return for treatment at the hospital and negatively affect the hospital's image (Handayani et al., 2024). Patient satisfaction with health services can be defined as the gap between the performance of the health service institution and patient expectations (Mursyid et al., 2024).

Outpatient services are services provided by medical and non-medical personnel to patients visiting hospital clinics (Hardini et al., 2025). The first point of contact for patients at a healthcare institution is the outpatient registration process, as this is the first interaction between patients and staff (Umi et al., 2024).

The hospital pharmacy installation is one of the health service units that directly interacts with patients, making it essential to maintain its continuity and service functions (Setyorini et al., 2025). Health workers are expected to provide the best possible service to create satisfaction among patients and the community in general (Setyorini et al., 2025).

Service quality can be measured using the SERVQUAL method, a service quality framework developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry. SERVQUAL is built upon comparing two main factors: customer perceptions of actual services received and their expectations. The five dimensions developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry include Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy (Sinollah et al., 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted at the Outpatient Pharmacy Installation of RSUD Tora Belo, Sigi Regency, in September–October 2025.

This study employed an analytical survey method with a cross-sectional approach. The independent variables were tangible, responsiveness, reliability, empathy, and assurance, while the dependent variable was patient satisfaction.

The study population included all outpatient pharmacy patients at RSUD Tora Belo who met the eligibility criteria. Based on outpatient visit data for 2024, there were 19,567 patients.

The sample consisted of 400 outpatient pharmacy patients at RSUD Tora Belo, Sigi Regency

Data were obtained through interviews using a questionnaire adapted from Umam, Muchlisoh, and Maryati (2019). Primary data were collected through direct interviews with respondents. The questionnaire produced values reflecting the actual service quality received by patients and their expectations regarding pharmaceutical service quality

Logistic regression analysis was used to describe the relationship between a dichotomous response variable (nominal or ordinal with two categories) and a set of predictor variables that may be continuous or categorical

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis examined the influence of independent variables: Tangible, Responsiveness, Reliability, Empathy, and Assurance on the dependent variable, overall patient satisfaction (Table 1.).

Table 1. Variables in the Equation

VariabelBebas	B	S.E	Wald	df	Sig	EXP (B)	95% C.I.for EXP (B)	
							Lower	Upper
Tangible	3.118	,965	10.443	1	,001	22.603	3.411	149.791
Responsiveness	2.226	1.037	4.612	1	,032	9.262	1.215	70.633
Reliability	3.132	,980	10.213	1	,001	22.922	3.357	156.492
Empathy	3.062	,963	10.120	1	,001	21.378	3.240	141.050
Assurance	,317	1.078	,145	1	,768	1.374	,166	11.367
Constans	-6.619	1.976	11.223	1	,001	,001		

Regression analysis using the Wald test showed the following:

Tangible: p-value = 0.001 (<0.05), indicating a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Exp(B) = 22.603, meaning inadequate tangible aspects may increase the risk of 22.603 dissatisfied patients.

Responsiveness: p-value = 0.032 (<0.05), indicating a significant effect. Exp(B) = 9.262, meaning poor responsiveness may increase dissatisfaction by 9.262 patients.

Reliability: p-value = 0.001 (<0.05), showing a significant effect. Exp(B) = 22.922, meaning unreliability may increase dissatisfaction by 22.922 patients.

Empathy: p-value = 0.001 (<0.05), indicating a significant effect. Exp(B) = 21.378, meaning low empathy may increase dissatisfaction by 21.378 patients.

Assurance: p-value = 0.768 (>0.05), indicating no significant effect on patient satisfaction. Exp(B) = 21.378, showing no meaningful increase in dissatisfaction if assurance is not improved.

Of the 400 distributed questionnaires, 20 were excluded due to incomplete, inconsistent, or outlier data, resulting in 380 valid responses for analysis.

Tangible aspects had a significant impact on patient satisfaction. Thus, improving physical facilities and staff appearance is a strategic factor for enhancing satisfaction at the Pharmacy

Installation of RSUD Tora Belo. Investments in waiting room improvements, cleanliness, comfort, and professional staff appearance can significantly increase patient satisfaction.

Conceptually, responsiveness refers to the ability of service providers to deliver prompt, accurate, and responsive services (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In hospital pharmacies, medication waiting time is a dominant indicator of service quality. Patients tend to feel satisfied when services are delivered without delays and staff demonstrate attentiveness in explaining medication information.

Several studies in Indonesia support these findings. Afrioza (2020) showed that responsiveness significantly affects patient satisfaction in health centers, especially in service speed. Rohmah (2021) found similar results, emphasizing timely prescription processing and responsiveness in addressing patient concerns. These findings suggest that improving responsiveness—shortening waiting times, enhancing staff coordination, and improving communication skills—is crucial for increasing satisfaction at RSUD Tora Belo.

Reliability was also found to be a strong predictor of patient satisfaction. Studies by Adriansyah et al. (2019), Putri et al. (2021), and Faradila (2020) highlight reliability's role in accurate medication dispensing, service consistency, and patient safety. Therefore, RSUD Tora Belo should prioritize improvements in reliability through stronger SOPs, competency training, double-check systems, SIMRS optimization, and consistent medication availability.

Empathy was another significant predictor of satisfaction. Studies by Wulandari et al. (2020), Septiana et al. (2021), Al-Abri et al. (2014), and Dagger & Sweeney (2007) support the critical role of personal attention, interpersonal communication, and humanistic service. RSUD Tora Belo should enhance humanistic approaches through communication training, ethical service reinforcement, improved counseling skills, and patient-friendly service culture.

Assurance did not have a significant effect on patient satisfaction, consistent with Setiawan et al. (2020) and Surya et al. (2021). Patients may assume staff competence as a basic standard and focus more on tangible service attributes such as speed, availability of medicines, and clarity of informations

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V. CONCLUSIONS

Four service quality dimensions: tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, and empathy significantly contribute to patient satisfaction with pharmaceutical services at Tora Belo General Hospital, while assurance does not. Efforts to improve service quality should prioritize facility enhancement, timely and accurate service delivery, and more empathetic patient interactions.

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